
Deliverable D2.1
Cross-fertilization workshop report – v1

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Abstract:	This deliverable is the first of a set of deliverables describing the results from the three cross-fertilization workshops that are planned in the project, in both their public and private sessions. This is the result of task T2.1.
Keyword List:	Cross-fertilization, discussion Forum, workshop
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Terms and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SW	Software
SwForum.eu .eu	European Forum of the software research community

Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the first result produced by task T2.1 - Cross-fertilization Workshops organisation, in the context of the SwForum.eu project. The main objective of the task is to organize and deliver three workshops involving stakeholders from both academia, industry and the public sector, representing different domains and application sectors. The workshops are important events to facilitate synergy-ignition among R&D EC funded projects as well as a dissemination opportunity.

Within the context of the initial 10 months of the project, taking advantage of the new way of holding meetings in the COVID era, we have modified our objectives and run two workshops instead of one. This has allowed us to reach our stakeholders early on (the first workshop being held in February). Moreover, it has allowed us to test two different approaches, one based on the invitation of well-known keynote speakers and the other approach more oriented to facilitate the discussion among participants.

1 Introduction

SwForum.eu aims to create a self-sustainable online forum that facilitates and encourages both researchers and practitioners as well as projects in software, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity to create intersections of expertise and a multidisciplinary approach to research and innovation. This forum seeks to set in place the European research roadmap and offer cross-fertilisation of competencies to all other research and innovation areas.

SwForum.eu works to enhance the visibility and competitiveness of research and innovation in the field of software technologies, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity, especially European funded Research and Innovation Action (RIA) projects. Moreover, the project aims to introduce best practices and technology transfer opportunities to cross-synergise European excellence.

SwForum.eu project runs from 1 October 2020 through 31 March 2023.

The main objective of the SwForum.eu project is to raise awareness and strengthen the competitiveness of the European Software Industry - including the underlying digital infrastructures together with the needed security mechanisms - by facilitating a sustainable European Forum for stakeholders representing scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators and policy-makers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity, where assets (products, services, technologies) can be shared, lessons learned, and policies developed, and facilitating engagement in the development of a set of research and innovation roadmaps for the Future Secure Digital Continuum through an online platform.

Within this context, SwForum.eu will promote EU cross-fertilization between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. This goal will be achieved by organizing a self-sustainable Forum (Objective 2 in the Grant Agreement) in the context of which workshops on specific cross-fertilization themes will be organized and will be driven toward the publication of joint papers, joint policy papers around the topics, the creation of new initiatives, and the launch of new ideas.

The aim is to create a living Forum that will involve, on a voluntary basis, individuals (researchers, industry representatives and end-users) interested in the future of EU research and innovation actions in the context of software technologies. In order to engage and increase stakeholder participation, SwForum.eu proposes to create a Fellowship programme, which will serve to maintain a fluid pool of experts from a balanced set of SwForum.eu target stakeholder groups. This group of high-profile, acknowledged experts in their respective domains will create an attractive “pull” effect on potential participants in these activities and events and maintain a high level of excellence in the interactions within the Forum. The Forum will contribute to the definition of the future European research roadmaps and will, in general, stay in touch with the EC to provide inputs, highlight needs from multiple stakeholders, and the like. SwForum.eu will promote the creation of this Forum, will drive it for the first period and, most importantly, it will drive the definition of a self-sustaining governance strategy and business model that will permit the sustainability of the organisation to survive beyond the end of the project.

So, the SwForum.eu is:

- ▣ A unique opportunity for European software researchers to discuss topics, issues, trends, concerns.
- ▣ A way to make our voices heard by developing recommendations to feed into policy-making decision processes.
- ▣ A professional online platform for:
 - Identifying topical groups
 - Creating profiles
 - Developing discussion threads
 - Likes/ dislikes/ recommending

1.1 About this deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is twofold: report about the organization and execution of the cross-fertilization workshops we have held in the first project period and 2) reflect on lessons learnt in order to start planning the organization of the forthcoming workshops.

1.2 Document structure

This document is organized as follows:

- ▣ Section 2 presents the first SwForum.eu workshop in terms of goals, achieved results, and considerations.
- ▣ Section 3 focuses on the second SwForum.eu workshop following the same structure used for the first one.
- ▣ Section 4 presents the lessons learnt together with a plan for the next workshops.
- ▣ Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions and Annex 1 provides the list of all links to the relevant material produced during the two workshops.

2 The First SwForum.eu workshop

The First SwForum.eu workshop¹ was held on 23 - 25 March 2021 and focused on Trustworthy Software and Open Source. The stated aim of the event was to trigger discussion around the relationship between trustworthiness and open source tools and methods to support the development of software. The workshop was quite successful and has captured the interest of a significant number of researchers and practitioners in the area. The discussion and exchange of ideas was very lively and useful as a basis to create a community. In the following we present more in detail the articulation of the workshop theme (Section 2.1), the workshop format and the call for papers (Section 2.2), the resulting program (Section 2.3), a description of the workshop execution (Section 2.4), and the material collected after the end of the workshop (Section 2.5).

2.1 The theme

The workshop theme has been chosen after having an internal discussion in the SwForum.eu team and based on the inputs received by our Project Officer. The initial idea was to focus on open source and on how to support this approach in a sustainable way. Then we decided to combine these topics with trustworthiness as we realized that even within our project there was a debate between those partners who were considering open-source software untrusted by definition and the ones who were considering that the transparency offered by open source is an important element to achieve trustworthiness.

Nowadays, the increasing importance of software for business, industry and life of common citizens makes the notion of trustworthiness a crucial one. A trustworthy software is one for which some important properties such as correctness, compliance, reliability, availability, performance, safety, security, maintainability, privacy of data, energy efficiency, sustainability, and certified interaction with humans are ensured [1].

In this context, several problems require attention from the research and practitioner's community. Among others, the workshop aimed at focusing on the following ones:

Characteristics of trustworthy software. Examples of attributes that make software trustworthy are security, compatibility, quality, correctness, dependability. Is there any other? What are the minimal characteristics of a trustworthy piece of software? The acceptable level of trustworthiness for a piece of software depends on the specific application domain the software is developed for. Is it possible to define a taxonomy?

Developing trustworthy software. Which methodologies, methods and tools are currently available to develop trustworthy software? Which are the most critical trustworthiness characteristics to be considered during development? How a developer or a final user can verify if and to which extent it is possible to trust on the used software? Which are the steps to be accomplished in this case? Could these tasks be automated?

The role of open source in the development of trustworthy software. At a first glance, open source may be seen as a development practice that is against the idea of trustworthiness: the first question we may ask, in fact, is how could I trust that an obscure developer is developing software I can trust? The situation is not as simple as it can appear. Open-source development today is not conducted by obscure individuals, but, often, it is supported by multiple enterprises sharing the same interest and/or by well-known and highly rewarded groups of independent developers [2, 3]. In many cases, open-source software could be even seen as more trustworthy than closed source one as only the first one can be inspected and analysed by third parties in a completely open and transparent manner [4]. So, the questions that we wanted to discuss concern: 1) what are the criteria to consider an open-source software trustworthy? 2) What

¹ <https://swforum.eu/events/first-swforumeu-workshop-trustworthy-software-and-open-source>

drives the industry to use and rely (or not) on open-source software? 3) How can an H2020 project develop an effective and impactful open-source software, considering its typical timeframe and scope?

2.2 The format and call for contribution

The workshop format was conceived to be highly interactive, with a good part of the agenda dedicated to soliciting discussion within the audience. We decided to invite four well-known experts to give keynote speakers to set the stage and, at the same time, to issue an open call for contribution.

2.2.1 Keynote speakers

The keynote speakers chosen were selected to ensure a good blend of different topics and ensuring a good geographical distribution. The choice fell on the following well-known speakers that has been able to cover in depth the workshop theme:

Tony Wasserman (Carnegie Mellon University, USA) is a professor of Software Management Practice in the Integrated Innovation Institute (III) and the executive director of the Center for Open Source Investigation at Carnegie Mellon University Silicon Valley (CMU-SV). From 2010-16, he served as a director of the Open Source Initiative (opensource.org). Tony has also a longstanding interest in innovation and entrepreneurship, which is reflected in his classes, and as an advisor to numerous startups. Tony was invited for his long lasting experience with open source and with the development of trustworthy software.

Roberto di Cosmo (IRILL, France) is a Computer Science full professor at University Paris Diderot, where he was head of doctoral studies for Computer Science from 2004 to 2009. A trustee of the IMDEA Software institute, and member of the national committee for Open Science in France, he is currently on leave at INRIA. Following the evolution of our society under the impact of IT with great interest, he is a long-term Free Software advocate, contributing to its adoption since 1998 with the best-seller Hijacking the world, seminars, articles and software. He created in 2015, and now directs Software Heritage, an initiative to build the universal archive of all the source code publicly available, in partnership with UNESCO.

Frank Karlitschek (Nextcloud, Germany) is a long-time open source developer. In 2016 he founded Nextcloud to create a fully open source and decentralized alternative to big centralized US cloud companies. In 2012 he initiated the User Data Manifesto to define basic human rights regarding personal data. He is also a fellow of Open Forum Europe and an advisor to the United Nations regarding Intellectual Property and Open Source.

Matthias Eckermann (SUSE, Germany) is Head of Product Management Linux Platforms at SUSE. Besides Security and Certification aspects, the primary focus is the adaptable SUSE Linux Enterprise products family. Matthias has more than 25 years of experience working with Linux and other Open Source projects. Special areas of interest include Linux filesystems and security technologies.

2.2.2 Call for papers and evaluation process

As mentioned, we opened the workshop to the submission of contributions by experts in the community. More specifically, the following submissions were welcome:

- 📄 *Position papers* in which authors could describe their position in a specific topic relevant to the workshop subject.
- 📄 *Technical papers* in which the authors could present some technical results about their studies in trustworthy or open-source software.
- 📄 *Demo papers* in which the authors could present their open-source tools where trustworthiness is relevant.

- *Panel proposals* specifying the topic to be discussed, why they could be considered relevant in this workshop, and the list of panelists.

The submissions were assessed by the workshop Program Committee for their relevance to the workshop topics and their potential impact in the discussion. The program committee members were the following ones:

- Giuseppe Cascavilla, Eindhoven University of Technology (The Netherlands)
- Cristina Chesta, Concept Reply (Italy)
- Ana Juan Ferrer, ATOS SA (Spain)
- Nicolas Ferry, University Côte d'Azur (France)
- Xavier Franch, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain)
- Giovanni Frattini, Engineering Ingegneria Informatica (Italy)
- Francisco Gortazar, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (Spain)
- Indika Kumara, TU/e - Jheronimus Academy of Data Science (The Netherlands)
- Zoltán Ádám Mann, University Duisburg-Essen (Germany)
- Anna Perini, Fondazione Bruno Kessler (Italy)
- Dana Petcu, West University of Timisoara (Romania)
- Jacopo Soldani, University of Pisa (Italy)
- Vlado Stankovski, University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)
- Cédric Thomas, OW2

They were coordinated by two program chairs from Politecnico di Milano, Elisabetta Di Nitto and Pierluigi Plebani.

After a thorough evaluation, the Program Committee decided to accept all submissions for presentation. Six of them have been also accepted for publication in the CEUR post-proceedings (<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2878/>).

2.3 The program

The workshop was organized in three sessions of 1.5 hours held over the three days (<https://swforum.trust-itservices.dev/workshop-programme>). The first two sessions have featured two keynotes each followed by one or two paper presentations. The last session was focused only on paper presentations.

Tuesday, March 23 2021

16:00 - 16:10	Welcome address by SWForum.eu and the European Commission
16:10 - 16:40	Open Source Software is Eating the World (keynote) <i>Tony Wasserman</i>
16:40 - 17:10	Open Source as Basis for the Secure Software Supply Chain (keynote) <i>Matthias Eckermann</i>
17.10 - 17.20	The Role of Government in Offering Trustworthy Open Source to Citizens (paper presentation) <i>Gianfranco Cecconi and Esther Huyer</i>
17:20 - 17:30	Discussion

Wednesday, March 24 2021

16:00 - 16:30	Software Heritage: A Revolutionary Infrastructure for Open Source <i>Roberto Di Cosmo</i>
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16:30 - 17:00	The Importance of Open Source Software for Digital Sovereignty, Research and Europe Overall <i>Frank Karlitschek</i>
17:00 - 17:10	A Dataset of Open-Source Safety-Critical Software (paper presentation) <i>Rafaila Galanopoulou and Diomidis Spinellis</i>
17.10 - 17.20	Approaches to the Integration of TRUST and FAIR Principles (paper presentation) <i>Jaime Delgado, Celia Alvarez Romero, Alicia Martínez García and Carlos Luis Parra Calderón</i>
17:20 - 17:30	Discussion

Thursday, March 25 2021

16:00 - 16:10	MEDINA: Improving Cloud Services trustworthiness through continuous audit-based certification (paper presentation) <i>Juncal Alonso, Jesús Luna Garcia, Leire Orue-Echevarria and Christian Banse</i>
16:10 - 16:20	CLAIMED, a Visual and Scalable Component Library for Trusted AI (paper presentation) <i>Romeo Kienzler and Ivan Nestic</i>
16:20 - 16:30	Programming Trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a Secure Framework (paper presentation) <i>Juncal Alonso, Christophe Joubert, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Matteo Pradella and Daniel Vladusic</i>
16:30 - 16:40	A Smart Development Environment for Infrastructure as Code (paper presentation) <i>Jesús Gorroñoigoitia, Zoe Vasileiou, Emilio Imperiali, Indika Kumara, Dragan Radolović and Georgios Meditskos</i>
16:40 - 17:10	Discussion
17:10 - 17:30	Planning for Future Joint Activities

2.4 The workshop execution

2.4.1 Summary of Day 1 (23 March 2021) discussion

The session chair, Pierluigi Plebani, has introduced the three main goals of the SwForum.eu project:

- ❏ To create a sustainable forum for software practitioners that last for the duration of the project;
- ❏ To define a research roadmap in mainly 3 areas: software technologies, digital infrastructure, and cybersecurity.
- ❏ To prepare H2020 projects that are opened with the focus to the market, to understand how to address the market with respect to the technology.

Luis Carlos Busquets Pérez (EU commission) introduction

Dr. Busquets Pérez has introduced the importance of Open-Source software in our world today. Emerging ICT systems which require more integration are a challenge not only for the hardware itself, but also for the software. Achieving seamless connectivity in a highly complex and dynamic environment is not easy. Moreover, the world is asking for more trust, security, reliability and processing of PB data. Many stakeholders are active in this domain and the challenge they face

is so powerful that no one alone can actually face it. There is a relevance and importance to coordination in areas of software security, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity. The objective of the SwForum.eu is precisely to act in way as a coordination mechanism for research projects and activities for dissemination of project results, organizing events like this one, policy events as well as roadmaps. The importance is to build a sustainable forum that acts without public funding, where stakeholders realise the importance of continuing acting once the EU funding has finished.

Nowadays, we cannot not speak about software without speaking about Open Source. With 50 years more experience we know that Open Source is here to stay, giving more market opportunities. It is important to see how we could do more business out of the Open-Source systems and how internalizing things that have been developed by Open-Source communities will assure that we supply more value to our customers, at the same or lower price, or at least at lower cost to us, so we can maximize our profit.

Open Source has succeeded, but in a very different way that was foreseen. Indeed, nowadays every business in ICT is considering Open Source for its strategic role and we must think how business can be made out of it.

So, SwForum.eu is a project for software engineering coordination and there are numerous technology trends that are happening now and have major impact on the development of software. Apart from Open Source, there is also in this trend Big Data, DevOps, Cloud Computing and Cybersecurity. All these topics represent highly dynamic environment and market segments and key drivers for innovation. The EC takes very seriously having a competitive landscape on the continent and encourages us to continue working in that direction and toward ICT and in software which is one of the economic sectors within the biggest economies of scale. As a prime industrial differentiator and as the basis for products and services software can significantly increase competitiveness and therefore, we certainly seek to increase the Europe competitiveness to achieve better growth and better wealth fare.

EC is committed to invest in software. ICT research is crucial to keep up Europe at the cutting edge of technologies.

Keynote by Tony Wasserman

The first keynote speaker, Tony Wasserman, has presented the “Open source is Eating the World”. The main questions that were raised was: does modern societies depend on software? Actually, we could not do anymore business without e-commerce and electronic stack purchases and even hiring personnel. We must think how dependent we are if we get in a situation when software systems go down, we could not make airlines ticket reservations, check in the hotels, and it becomes really something quite unworkable in a high-tech society.

On the one hand, we have these systems rarely updated and on the other hand, we have apps that are updated at a high frequency mainly for new functionalities, but often to fix a bug. But let face it. People expect software to be reliable and trustworthy, we all expect security into systems. Are AI/ ML applications really trustworthy?

Software organizations are evaluating both proprietary and open-source systems concurrently. A current investigation showed that software organizations are using only 37% of security tools so, they are vulnerable at risks. However, in order to build a trustworthy software, we need to rely more on the security tools.

The main takeaways from the discussion are as follows:

- ▣ FOSS use is not just mainstream, but nearly universal and requires organizational governance.
- ▣ Trustworthiness is independent of proprietary versus open-source code.

- ❏ All software projects should analyse their code to reduce static code problems and other vulnerabilities prior to deployment.

Keynote by Matthias Eckermann

Eckerman has presented the topic: “Open Source as a basis for the secure software supply chain”. The available solutions for a secure supply in the Open-Source world were discussed in four steps:

1. What does "Secure Software Supply Chain" mean?
2. Why you need to ensure a Secure Software Supply Chain?
3. Traditional and container native approaches
4. Open-Source assets

Eckerman gave an extended definition of the Digital Sovereignty: the ability to secure, document and trace source and binaries, build environment and updates mechanisms of a specific workload over its full life cycle, to gain trust into and keep control over machines, processes, businesses, human beings, and data.

Further on, he talked about which components to consider as well as the universe of the three topics: Digital Sovereignty, Open-Source initiatives, and Secure Software Supply Chain. They represent part of the quality in the Supply Chain. He took the DevOps as a template to discuss the software life cycle through the plan and code, build and test, release, deploy and operate, and maintain phases. The presenter has also pointed out some initiatives and projects like Git, Public code repository, Linux Foundation, and Open Build Service.

For instance, Open Build Service features and benefits were presented as follow:

Features:

- ❏ Free and Open Source
- ❏ Reproducible builds
- ❏ 100+ users/ companies worldwide
- ❏ Developed by open SUSE and SUSE

Benefits:

- ❏ Full visibility in how SUSE builds and maintains
- ❏ Enables community to build/ maintain
- ❏ Enables and enforces processes
- ❏ Other processes build upon
- ❏ Trust

As a final remark, the keynote speaker discussed how the three topics interrelate in terms of software, business models and Data and how with bringing all together we are building trust into the software that we want to use.

Paper presentation by Gianfranco Cecconi and Esther Hyer and final discussion

This presentation focused on “What’s the role of government in offering trustworthy open source to citizens”. It was discussed the experience in building a software, particularly with focus on trustworthiness.

At the end of the presentation, the discussion continued with a broad focus on all presentations of the day. The following questions were touched upon:

- ❏ What is Open Data anyway?
- ❏ The roots of EU’s commitment to data run deep.
- ❏ The European Data portal offering European countries and institutions data to citizens and unleashing its value.

- ❑ How to achieve correctness by maximizing the re-user base.
- ❑ Focus effort on relevant and achievable compliance.
- ❑ In what way to broaden the understanding and measurement of performance?

Incentives and education developed the necessary awareness to make the most out of data resources reuse. The time has matured for European software portal. Open-source observatory has already existed.

Part of the discussion was also dedicated to the importance of the legislation and government standards. Legislation cannot necessarily guarantee a direct link between liability and the license.

2.4.2 Summary of Day 2 (24 March 2021) discussion

Keynote by Roberto di Cosmo

Roberto di Cosmo gave a keynote speech on “Software Heritage – A revolutionary infrastructure for Open Source”. A permanent archive of open software like Software Heritage is important for the work of researchers developing or maintaining research software: research software engineers (RSEs), and with that, for research as a whole. This initiative aims at building an archive of all Open-Source code that is publicly available. The first accent was put on whether the Open Source is growing and where does the reused software come from?

Key issues that have been raised were:

- ❑ Findability: what code is relevant for the application?
- ❑ Availability: can we get this code now, tomorrow, in 20 years?
- ❑ Integrity: is this really the right code? Needs crypto?
- ❑ Traceability: where are the parts of this system coming from? Needs a global provenance database.
- ❑ Reproducibility: can we reliably rebuild everything? Needs ground-braking tools
- ❑ Traceability, safety, security, etc.
- ❑ We need a global coordinated effort and a common, open, shared infrastructure to track all software.

Software heritage was created some 15 years ago with a clear and precise mission which is to collect and share all software source code, preserving our heritage, enabling better software and better science for all. This is just a part of the mission. The big part of the mission is to build and enable infrastructure to better track and to build better software in science for all in the society.

The aim of the Software Heritage is to be a reference catalogue for all software source code, important being to build universal archive (to preserve all software source code), last but not least is that it is a building block for creating a research infrastructure that allows to explore all software source code. Overall, this was the Software Heritage presented in a nutshell.

Some selected use cases were presented as well as, there was a discussion on the quality assurance mechanisms, and how to quality-assure the code.

Keynote by Frank Karlitschek

The next talk was on the “Importance of Open-Source Software”. The presenter touched upon three most important public Cloud concerns as well as a definition on the Digital Sovereignty and Cyber Sovereignty. Data needs to be controlled and it is necessary to define basic rights for people to control their own data in the Internet age. Another part of the data is coming from Machine Learning. It was raised the question: What can we do to protect the data and guarantee digital sovereignty.

Further on, it was mentioned about the initiative by German, French and other European governments for decentralised Cloud infrastructure (Gaia-X), Open standards (and free software), On-premise/ off-premise (to use Cloud providers). Europe should invest in an Open-Source economy and market, because it is really something that can give people freedom and possibility to innovate. Digital Sovereignty is mandatory for a free and open society. The free software is the key to Digital Sovereignty.

Paper presentation by Rafaila Galanopoulou

It was also presented a paper entitled “A Dataset of Open-Source Safety–Critical Software” with the motivation of this study being:

- ❏ Open-Source software allows the study of safety-critical:
 - Software code
 - Software development processes
 - Reusable components
- ❏ A body of such software must first be established

It was also outlined the methodology and the guidelines for future work on defect prediction metrics per category.

Paper presentation by Jaime Delgado

Another presentation was with title “Approaches to the integration of TRUST and FAIR principles”. The FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) were presented as well as TRUST principles vs. FAIRification and the FAIRification tools (Data Curation Tool, Data Privacy Tool). As well, the TRUST principles to implement on Open-Source software (Transparency, Responsibility, User community, Sustainability, Technology) were outlined, as well. It was highlighted that it is very important to follow methodology in which TRUST and FAIR are both working together.

2.4.3 Summary of Day 3 (25 March 2021) discussion

The final day at the First SwForum.eu workshop was focused on the topic of cybersecurity software technologies and digital infrastructures.

Paper presentation by Leire-Orue Echevarria

Firstly, it was presented the MEDINA project which is focused on areas of Cloud security certification and audit evidence management to create a continuous security certification framework. Reasons that have been mentioned for low adoption of Cloud services in Europe were risk of a security breach, data storage localization, legal jurisdiction, insufficient skills, lack of interoperability. Within this context an important question has been raised: “could the certification be a solution”? There were mentioned several regulations and initiatives that have been launched by the EC to promote the adoption of Cloud Computing and avoid fragmentation in certification approaches. Within the project scope of MEDINA it was also mentioned the importance to comply with the EU cybersecurity act and European Cloud services certification scheme. So, MEDINA focuses primarily on the automation of security requirements (identified as high), although there are some requirements at the substantial level that also need an automation. The outlined approach was to define first the metrics, select controls, specify the certification language, collect and evaluate evidence, and continuous auditing. Finally, the results of MEDINA project were presented.

Paper presentation by Juncal Alonso Ibarra

The next presentation was on the research paper “Programming trustworthy Infrastructure-as-code in a Secure Framework”. The paper focused on the on-going project PIACERE which aims to increase the productivity of DevOps teams, enabling to fully embrace the Infrastructure-as-

Code approach. The main points touched upon were the context and motivation as well as the project's objectives, the approach and workflow, the general challenges of PIACERE project, the outcomes and innovations.

So, Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) enables the automation of several deployment, configuration and management tasks that otherwise would have to be performed manually by an operator. Obviously, the DevSecOps and DevOps movement is so important. The purpose is to put IaC in the middle of the traditional DevOps loop as well as to support the modelling of the infrastructural resources and to help developers to characterize these infrastructural elements. The best combination of infrastructural elements could be selected by means of multi-objective algorithms and AI-based techniques. Once we have emulated the code and selected the best infrastructural schemas then we automatically orchestrate deployment by deploying containers, for instance. At the run time we also want to analyse, monitor and apply re-deployment if necessary. The presentation was closed by pointing out the PIACERE ongoing results.

Paper presentation by Jesús Gorroñoitia

Cloud Computing is amateur paradigm that has evolved to accommodate ever-increasing complex applications as in the AI and HPC domain. The final presentation for Day 3 of the SwForum.eu EU was on the paper "SODALITE: A Smart Development Environment for Infrastructure-as-a-Code". The SODALITE motivation is the trustworthy deployment of complex app topologies in heterogeneous infrastructures. The modelling roles and DSLs were outlined. It was also discussed the SODALITE Smart IDE approach with respect to editors, and in-sync multi-view representations, KB-powered modelling assistance and validation. The approach considers also the modelling environment, IaC and run time. Tool that assists modelers with the trustworthy deployment of their complex apps in heterogeneous scenarios was also presented.

Workshop concluding remarks

Concluding remarks for Day 3 of the workshop were about future plans for dissemination and other future connected activities, as well as the importance of building a long-lasting organization. It was also underlined the importance to restart the activity of the Software Engineering for services and applications cluster in terms of initiatives aiming at creating a community of the projects in the area of software and at identifying and characterising new challenges for future research. SwForum.eu will try to act as driving force toward this objective.

2.4.4 Participants

The first SwForum.eu workshop had a total of 86 registrants from 23 countries, made up of 20 women, 60 men and 6 not specified. Registrants included participants from 21 different European Funded software, cybersecurity and digital infrastructure projects.

2.4.5 Summary of the discussion

The highlights from the discussion during the First SwForum.eu EU are as follows:

- ❏ Coordination & cross-Pollination across all major stakeholders (researchers, industry representatives and end-users, policy making and regulatory institutes) is needed and SwForum.eu could take a role in this endeavour.
- ❏ The growth of the EU Software Technology Research Ecosystem leading to European Leadership on a global stage must be monitored and encouraged.
- ❏ The creation of an Innovation Road Map for EC Policy Makers strengthening the European Digital Single Market (DSM) could be welcomed.
- ❏ The tailored Market and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) methodology offered by the project could support the improvement of capacity building of industry players.

2.5 The post-workshop materials

2.5.1 The CEUR proceedings

Six papers are published as open access CEUR-WS proceedings at the following link: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2878/>.

2.5.2 The videos

The first SwForum.eu workshop was held virtually, aiming at triggering the discussion around trustworthy software, tools and methods to support its development. The SwForum.eu team has created the recorded video compilation of the event, ensuring to catch all the insightful information shared by the key speakers during the event and to share it with those who missed the event. So far there are 23 views of the recordings.

The workshop recordings per each day are available on the SwForum.eu videos and podcasts: <https://swforum.trust-it-services.dev/outreach/videos-podcasts/swforumeu-workshop-2021>

Figure 1. SwForum.eu Workshop 2021

3 The Second SwForum.eu workshop

The second SwForum.eu workshop² focused on Research Challenges, Collaboration, and Coordination among European Software Engineering Projects and was held online from 29th of June 2021 to the 1st of July 2021.

3.1 The theme and the format

The purpose of the Second SwForum.eu workshop was threefold:

1. to discuss open research challenges that are of interest to the European Software Engineering community;
2. to discuss collaboration opportunities among European projects in the area of software engineering;
3. to understand how to develop a self-sustaining and self-governed research forum at a European level.

To achieve these objectives we have decided to open a call for contributions to collect research challenges (see Section 3.2) and to invite projects to introduce themselves at the workshop so to start the discussion about collaboration opportunities and the development of a long-lasting research forum. Given the focus on European Software Projects and our decision not to invite well-known speakers, we were expecting a smaller number of participants in order to keep the discussion focused.

3.2 The call for contribution and accepted challenges

The call for contribution was open to challenges concerning any software topic. For each challenge we were asking the proponents to provide:

- ▣ The context/application domain in which the challenge is relevant
- ▣ The definition of the challenge
- ▣ Why it is important
- ▣ What the proponents want to achieve from the discussion
- ▣ How the proponents think the discussion around the challenge should have been organized

The submitted contributions have been evaluated by the members of the SwForum consortium as the purpose was not to be highly selected but, rather, to exclude, if needed, clearly meaningless submissions. In the end, we decided to accept all submitted challenges that were the following:

Challenge 1: An ecosystem for analysis software

Proponent: Michel Chaudron (Technical University of Eindhoven)

Context: International Research Collaboration on Software Engineering (esp. Reverse Software Architecting)

There are many specialized tools for analysis software - ranging from fact extraction (from various sources: code, design, test, issues, ...), tools for combining these, tool for combining and analysing the results and visualising the results. The majority of this research exists in islands of research groups. The community as a whole could improve their research (in terms of reach,

² <https://SwForum.eu/events/second-SwForum.eu-workshop>

replicability, transparency) by standing on each others' shoulders by building on other tools in the ecosystem. However, there is no actor that drives this integration.

We want to create a (community) for building an infrastructure for Integration and Sharing of Scientific Workflows on top of Shared Software (Engineering) Data

At the workshop we want to discuss:

1. How to build a community that supports this idea?
2. How to build the actual infrastructure which existing infrastructures can we build on top of?
3. Can we reuse from other disciplines (Medicine, Genetics, Biology, ...)?
4. What can be a sustainable funding-model?

Challenge 2: IaC Cost and Performance Optimization

Proponent: Alfonso de la Fuente (Prodevelop)

Context: H2020 PIACERE Project - Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a sEcuRE framework.

Multi-Objective optimization of costs, performance, availability, and resiliency for Cloud Applications matters because scale-in and out operations for elastic infrastructure provisioning are increasingly being automatized from a Software Configuration Management (SCM) perspective. Furthermore, multiple organizations confront the trial of minimizing unnecessary expenditures and extracting the most value from Cloud-based commercial applications, by means of Infrastructure as Code (IaC) management, through periods of both predictable and unpredictable demand.

With this discussion we aim at identifying the concepts, criteria and tools relevant to this problem.

Challenge 3: The role of AI in the edge-to-cloud context

Proponent: Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)

Context: Artificial Intelligence is becoming pervasive today, driven by the strong growth potential of AI software platforms which are expected to approach USD 11.8 billion in revenue at a CAGR of 35.3% by 2023 worldwide. Many of the benefits of this evolution come from using computing resources at the periphery of the network. Moreover, many companies are evaluating the use of edge computing for data collection, processing, and online analytics to reduce applications latency and data transfers. A growing number of use cases (e.g. predictive maintenance, machine vision, and healthcare) can benefit from AI applications spanning edge-to-cloud infrastructures leveraging resources available at the computing continuum. In this context, edge intelligence, i.e., edge-based inferencing, will become the foundation of all industrial AI applications while most new applications will involve some AI components at various levels of the computing continuum.

Challenges:

- 📦 How to enhance the flexibility of cloud-based solutions in order to accommodate new AI sensors and data while optimising performance?

- ❑ How to tackle the growing number of sensors and network devices and unpredictable size of data collected, thereby increasing computation efficiency and relieving the strain on cloud and edge resources to process huge amounts of data?
- ❑ How to cope with the variety of IoT devices and their trend to incorporate AI functionalities as new technology will bring even more diverse devices in terms of computing capacity and energy efficiency?
- ❑ How to address security and privacy concerns in terms of model training, their deployment and local data processing?

This is important because artificial intelligence (AI) is fast becoming a key driver of economic development, playing a major role in shaping global competitiveness and productivity over the next years. With the ever-increasing development of AI applications such as intelligent personal assistants, video/audio surveillance, smart cities' applications, autonomous driving and Industry 4.0, comes also a growing need to optimise the use of computational resources for data collection, processing, and online analytics, while at the same time preserving data privacy and increasing the security of data. AI-SPRINT will change the perspectives of several stakeholders:

- ❑ AI application developers: AI-SPRINT will help them easily implement new applications;
- ❑ System integrators: AI-SPRINT gives powerful yet flexible tools to develop multi-cloud systems including resources at the full computing continuum stack involving classic components and AI models;
- ❑ Cloud providers: they can benefit from tools for simplifying resource management also at the edge layer and for offering new PaaS AI services thanks to the availability of novel open-source design tools.

With this discussion we aim at finding points of collaboration with other projects that work in the same field.

3.3 The program

The second SwForum.eu workshop was organized in three one hour and half sessions according to following schedule (<https://swforum.eu/events/second-swforum.eu-workshop>):

29 June 2021, 16.00-17.30 CEST: Research Challenges in Software Engineering

16.00 - 17:00 What are the software engineering themes you think we should research in the future? To answer to this question, we discussed a selected set of challenges proposed by the workshop participants.

17:00 - 17.30 A possible taxonomy of projects based on the SwForum.eu .eu Radar

30 June 2021, 16.00-17.30 CEST: Collaboration opportunities

16.00 - 16.30 Two-minute elevator pitches, one per project/initiative

16:30 - 17.30 Discussion about possible collaborations among projects

1 July 2021 16.00-17.30 CEST: Coordination Plan

16.00 - 16.30 Open discussion to collect the needs from the European projects/initiatives

16.30 - 17.00 Presentation of the SwForum.eu idea for self-sustainable coordination

17.00 - 17.30 Discussion

3.4 The workshop execution

3.4.1 Figures about participants

The second SwForum.eu workshop had a total of 29 registrants from 10 countries, made up of 10 women, 17 men and 2 not specified. Registrants included participants from 10 different European Funded software, cybersecurity and digital infrastructure projects.

3.4.2 Summary of the discussion

As presented in Section 3.3 the workshop was divided in three days, with specific topics and objectives for each one. In this section the discussions held during the three days are summarized below.

3.4.2.1 Introduction into Day 1: Research Challenges in Software Engineering

During this first session two challenges among the three selected ones were presented. Each proposer presented his or her challenge for 10-15 minutes and then discussion was opened. Presentations used are included in annex 1. At the end of the session was presented the SwForum.eu Radar to classify and understand the software projects.

In the next paragraphs the main discussions are summarized:

 Challenge 1: An ecosystem for analysis software. Presentation by: Michel Chaudron

Nowadays there are multiple sources of open software and various tools for combining these sources, analysing, and visualising the results. The majority of this research exists in islands of research groups. The community as a whole could improve their research (in terms of reach, replicability, transparency) by standing on each other's shoulders by building on other tools in the ecosystem. However, there is no actor that drives this integration. The proposer wanted to create a (community) for building an infrastructure for integration and sharing of scientific workflows on top of shared software (engineering) data. He shared his experience in creating, collecting and sharing a database of UML models and Github projects that use UML. He and his group identified the need of extra elements to identify scientific workflows on top of the data extracted from the repositories of Software Design. One of the differentiating things in the software domain compared to others (i.e. physics, medicine) is that we do not work with passive things but with evolving project (even if you can make snapshots of it). The software projects are always evolving, community is adding changes, etc.

The models can be represented through different formats (graphical, uml notation). One of the difficulties of collecting information about these projects is the lack of a uniform notation.

The proposed result to overcome this challenge is described at architectural level as shown below (Fig. 1):

CoSARI Overview

Figure 1. CoSARI architecture project

From the requirements presented for this kind of tool it seems that some existing solutions could address these requirements but still these components should be “configured” somehow to provide relevant data.

Past projects such as software Heritage or Open Science Cloud are putting effort in this context, but they are not providing a framework as the proposed one.

Reproducibility is another thing to consider as many software projects rely on specific platforms.

The starting point: In other disciplines there are organizations driving that kind of platforms (i.e. CERN for physics). Is this applicable to software? For instance, Software Heritage could be one such organization. At European level, the institutions may help if you already have some collaboration happening in the topic. Another alternative is to use a European research project where several European organizations work on doing this kind of platform.

In the architecture the trickiest part could be the image processing needed to get the information from the models (they already have a prototype for this), as well as the ontology creation to support any kind of diagrams.

Challenge 2: IaC Cost and Performance Optimization. Presentation by Alfonso de la Fuente: Multi-Objective optimization of costs, performance, availability, and resiliency for Cloud Applications. That matters because scale-in and out operations for elastic infrastructure provisioning are increasingly being automatized from a Software Configuration Management (SCM) perspective. Furthermore, multiple organizations confront the trial of minimizing unnecessary expenditures and extracting the most value from Cloud-based commercial applications, by means of Infrastructure as Code (IaC) management, through periods of both predictable and unpredictable demand.

Things that can be optimized are:

1. Selection of the CSP
2. Performance

3. Cost

All these objectives need to be reconciled and have real run time data of the application performance to detect and predict events which will trigger new optimization processes. Not only run time data from the applications or the IaC considered are needed but also changes on the available resources (i.e. changes on the prizes, SLAs, etc.). The optimization actions need to consider the different level of granularity offered by the CSPs so the action is optimized for the specific CSP. PIACERE project is proposing an optimizing platform to tackle this challenge.

Figure 2. PIACERE architecture

IaC is linked to DevOps as IaC more related to infrastructural level is automating the creation and configuration of infrastructure through software.

As a wrap up of the session the assistants are requested to think about:

1. How to set up a framework to analyse the software projects?
2. Which other projects can collaborate on the IaC and Cost / Performance challenge that is proposed? Are DICE, DECIDE, SODALITE, RADON suitable ones?

Introduction on taxonomy of projects based on the SwForum.eu Radar: Presentation by David Wallom

Current existing visualization for projects are not very useful. The presented herewith Radar is trying to improve that by providing:

- Single point of entry and integrating with other information sources (i.e. the project website)
- Useful for different stakeholders: The projects, the European Commission, investors, etc.
- It provides clear and illustrative information.

This is achieved namely through a Technology Radar inspired in the ThoughtWorks radar but improved with new features (i.e. live radar, integrated with MTRL, etc.). The SwForum.eu is based in the one created for Cyberwatching.eu, but adapted and enlarged with new visualisation elements and capabilities from the lessons learnt as well as differing requirements. The Radar can present different types of projected related information as follows:

- Radar segments: You can view the whole radar or a radar segment.
- Radar rings
- blip position (within a ring) can encode some further information. A blip represents a project by a unique identifier (number).
- blip size i.e. to represent other information like the value of the project.
- blip shape,
- blip colour,
- filters, allow the use of multi complex taxonomies.

In SwForum.eu there will be three segments: Tools and techniques, platforms and frameworks. Projects may have more than one affiliation (segment) so we will use the blip to express this. See Figure 3 below.

- **Projects may have more than one affiliation to a taxonomy category.**

SWForum's Blip Position taxonomy:
Project blips shall be positioned within their respective Ring and Segment as follows:

- Centre of left third of segment**
Projects with a secondary classification positioned to the *left* of its primary classification segment
- Centre of segment axis**
Projects with only a primary classification
- Centre of right third of segment**
Projects with a secondary classification positioned to the *right* of its primary classification segment

Positioning within these thirds of a classification segment is not relevant within this granularity of classification.

Figure 3. Blip position in the SwForum.eu Radar

Radar rings are used to assess the project results with respect to a reference date in relation to the project ends.

Two blip shapes: Circle and triangle depending on when the project entered the radar (previous editions or new project).

The blip colour is used to express the MTRL level of the project (Figure 4).

SWForum's Blip Colour taxonomy:
Project blips in the radar shall be coloured using a single colour from a 3-colour palette as follows:

- A custom MRL scale shall be used as defined for SWForum.eu
- The original TRL scale of the MTRL framework shall be used with minor adjustment in interpretation
- A single numerical MTRL score shall be calculated as:
Score = MRL x TRL

Based on the numerical MTRL score, the blip will be coloured as follows:
Red for scores below 25;
Yellow for scores between 25 and 45 (inclusive); and
Green otherwise (46 and above).

Figure 4. Blip Colour Taxonomy

To further tag the projects the ACM computing classification system (only using 5 of the primary domains more relevant to SwForum.eu) is used as a filter in taxonomy.

The information of the projects represented in the Radar is linked to the information of the project presented in the project mini-site.

The idea is to work in collaboration with the projects to insert information about the projects, supporting them through that process.

3.4.2.2 Introduction into Day 2: Collaboration opportunities

During this day, the 3rd research challenge proposed by the AI-SPRINT H2020 project was presented. The presentation was followed by an open discussion involving all represented projects.

Challenge 3: The role of AI in the edge-to-cloud context. Presentation by Rita Giuffrida:

Artificial Intelligence is becoming pervasive today, driven by the strong growth potential of AI software platforms which are expected to approach USD 11.8 billion in revenue at a CAGR of 35.3% by 2023 worldwide. Many of the benefits of this evolution come from using computing resources at the periphery of the network. Moreover, many companies are evaluating the use of edge computing for data collection, processing, and online analytics to reduce applications latency and data transfers. A growing number of use cases (e.g. predictive maintenance, machine vision, and healthcare) can benefit from AI applications spanning edge-to-cloud infrastructures leveraging resources available at the computing continuum. In this context, edge intelligence, i.e., edge-based inferencing, will become the foundation of all industrial AI applications while most new applications will involve some AI components at various levels of the computing continuum. The challenges are as follows (see also Fig. 5):

- How to enhance the flexibility of cloud-based solutions in order to accommodate new AI sensors and data while optimising performance?
- How to tackle the growing number of sensors and network devices and unpredictable size of data collected, thereby increasing computation efficiency and relieving the strain on cloud and edge resources to process huge amounts of data?
- How to cope with the variety of IoT devices and their trend to incorporate AI functionalities as new technology will bring even more diverse devices in terms of computing capacity and energy efficiency?
- How to address security and privacy concerns in terms of model training, their deployment and local data processing?
- How to deal with the lack of expertise on AI?

Figure 5. AI challenges

This is important because artificial intelligence (AI) is fast becoming a key driver of economic development, playing a major role in shaping global competitiveness and productivity over the next years. With the ever-increasing development of AI

applications such as intelligent personal assistants, video/audio surveillance, smart cities' applications, autonomous driving and Industry 4.0, comes also a growing need to optimise the use of computational resources for data collection, processing, and online analytics, while at the same time preserving data privacy and increasing the security of data. AI-SPRINT proposes to create results to address this specific challenge as well as sub-challenges for several stakeholders:

- AI application developers: AI-SPRINT will help them easily implement new applications;
- System integrators: AI-SPRINT gives powerful yet flexible tools to develop multi-cloud systems including resources at the full computing continuum stack involving classic components and AI models;
- Cloud providers: they can benefit from tools for simplifying resource management also at the edge layer and for offering new PaaS AI services thanks to the availability of novel open-source design tools.

AI-Sprint will be applied to 3 use cases: Personalised healthcare, maintenance & inspection, farming 4.0. Apart from these other scenarios where edge computing and AI with time critical applications are:

- Smart driving
- Run-time offloading through the Cloud Continuum

For the healthcare use case the main challenges to be solved by the project are:

- the models are personalized for each single person,
- privacy preserving is critical
- the “wearable sensors” need to be really small but still run “complex” algorithms.

One of the potential results to advance on that could be to create a “cluster” of projects working on AI and Cloud Computing. To this respect the cluster would be cross-topic, involving energy efficiency, security, cloud computing, sensors (IoT) not only AI as such.

AI-SPRINT envision also to work on the guidelines about energy efficiency of AI usage because this is also a controversial topic as the more data you manage the more energy you consume.

During the second part of this day, the objective was to discuss about the collaboration opportunities for the projects represented in the workshop which were Full5G, DICE, SODALITE, PIACERE, RADON, MEDINA, EOSC, Policy Cloud, Gaia-X, Cyberwatching.eu.

During this session, supporting material was presented for the creation of the discussion and gathering the contributions and conclusions:

- 📌 Idea Boards (see section 3.5.1 for details). The projects could be linked to the proposed results so that the collaboration could be focused on specific results even if this “results-based” collaboration may be challenging due to the specificities of each solution, different stages of the project, or lack of information about the tools each project is using, etc.
- 📌 Initial analysis on common topics in the projects as described in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Initial analysis on common topics from the projects prepared by SwForum.eu for the workshop.

These topics could be the initial set for discussion in the forum but need to be refined and further levels of granularity need to be created to foster the collaboration between the projects. It could be also interesting to identify problems to each of the topics and select projects proposing solutions to these problems/challenges.

As a result of the discussion it emerged that one of the issues in the European Research projects is that as the knowledge is not shared the solutions are built from scratch. This is seen as a possible aspect where SwForum.eu could contribute, setting up repositories of reusable assets from projects.

3.4.2.3 Introduction into Day 3: Coordination Plan

The objective was to understand whether there was an interest in setting up a group around software engineering and how to organise that group. The group agreed that there is a hole in Europe for what concerns a group of people interested in Software Engineering with the purpose of creating impact in the European research agenda. If this interest exists, we need to understand further how to create the group and to maintain it during the time.

3.5 The post-workshop materials

3.5.1 The idea boards

As mentioned, the workshop was held online due to the pandemic situation. This has imposed a specific engagement, participation and dynamic of the workshop. Therefore, we decided to use the functionalities of “Idea Boards” to gather opinions and ideas.

The primary purpose of the idea boards is to brainstorm and collect ideas in a type of visual presentation or collage consisting of ideas and images in a composition. It serves as a place to gather all the relevant ideas and concepts related to a particular topic for discussion. These ideas are accessible for the entire group to see in a meeting. Main usages of idea boards are related

to quick brainstorming, team building and organizing suggestions and to facilitate the development of an idea.

Sticky notes are the simplest and most effective way to use the idea boards. These can be added to the board and moved, enlarged, removed quickly.

For the implementation of the idea boards in the second the SwForum.eu workshop we used the online service called “Idea Boardz”³. We created a board called *SwForum.eu 2nd Workshop* and we set up two groups where to create the notes.

1. Research challenges: Research challenges proposed by the participants.
2. Potential results: Results (mechanisms, tools, components, frameworks, techniques) proposed by the participants that can help us to overcome one or more of the proposed challenges.

Apart from the creation of the sticky notes we also set up the functionality for evaluating them by means of votes. With this approach the participants were able to vote for each of the sticky note so that the challenges and their relevance were gathered. The “IdeaBoardz” that we have created for the discussion of the second day is accessible in the following link:

<https://ideaboardz.com/for/SwForum.eu%202nd%20Workshop/3953572>, and a snapshot of it is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 7. Online idea board created in the Second SwForum.eu workshop

The overview of the information collected through the idea board session is shown in tables 1 and 2 below:

Table 1. Research challenges and votes from the Idea Board

Research challenges	Votes
Integration and Sharing of Scientific Workflows on top of Shared Software Data	4
The role of AI in the edge-to-cloud context	3
Multi-Objective optimization of costs, performance, availability, and resiliency for Cloud Applications.	3
Sharing reusable know-how and source code between ongoing and completed EU projects.	3
Testing serverless and cloud applications beyond performance/load testing.	2
Flexibility of Cloud-based solutions. Security and privacy concerns.	1
As per Leire, it is really hard to get public information. As a lesson learnt from the cyberwatching project, we can maximise the project hub by collecting the project information.	1
Categorisation by results could be a collaboration challenge however, it could be a good tagging option. Those results could be sub-categorised by "who could benefit from those results" with that we could identify the target audience per each result and group them by stakeholders.	1

³ <https://ideaboardz.com/>

Table 2. Potential solutions to solve the research challenges and votes from the Idea Board

Potential results	Votes
Building an infrastructure for Integration and Sharing of Scientific Workflows on top of Shared Software (Engineering) data	3
Catalogue of unified infrastructural elements	3
Tools/mechanisms to optimise the use of computational resources for data collection, processing, and online analytics,	2
Tools/mechanisms to preserve data privacy and increase the security of data from the IoT sensors	2
A 'Know-how' and source code sharing platform between projects that encompass complementary elements.	2
Tools, mechanisms to optimize the infrastructural configuration	1
Cloud based solutions in order to accommodate new AI sensors and data	1
Novel tools to test cloud applications beyond performance testing.	1

During the third day, we developed a new idea board that extends the first one and that aimed at soliciting new non research-oriented needs by the projects and hints about possible instruments to use. The result of the discussion is available here <https://ideaboardz.com/for/SwForum%20nd%20Workshop/3969028>. A screenshot of the board is available in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Second version of the Idea Board.

3.5.2 The videos

The presentations and discussions held during the workshop have been recorded as videos. They are available here: <https://swforum.trust-itservices.dev/outreach/videos-podcasts/second-swforumeu-workshop-research-challenges-collaboration-and>.

4 Lessons learnt and plan for the future workshops

From the experience gathered organizing the first two SwForum.eu workshops we have understood that the blend of keynote speakers and open calls seems to work better than just an open call. This is the case, in particular, when the speakers are well-known ones. This confirms also that the research fellowship programme we have put in place as part of the project is a useful one as it will allow us to host well-known speakers even during the in-presence events.

While project representatives are interested in participating and receiving inputs concerning the dissemination of their project results, their participation is not always active. Also, they are involved in multiple initiatives managed by different CSAs and interest groups and this implies that they have limited time to be proactively involved in all of them. For this reason, we will try to join forces with other initiatives, e.g., H-Cloud/Hub4Cloud, still respecting the peculiarities and mission of each of them.

Another important lesson we have learnt is that, even when events are meant to be online, they need to be prepared well in advance in order to make sure that attendees can participate and propose their contributions. Moreover, we had the impression that the audience is getting tired of online meetings (the so-called “Zoom fatigue”). Also, the schedule in the late afternoon might have not been suitable for all potential attendees.

As a last point, we realized that in order to increase the effectiveness of our workshops, the project itself needs to increase its visibility. A role that could allow us to do so is to act as a “news” spreader by redistributing the news generated by the projects we want to target. We should try to be active in this area and invest in the insertion of information in the mini-sites developed as part of the project. If SwForum.eu increases its visibility, there could be a good opportunity to convince projects that SwForum.eu is a good window from where project results can be disseminated.

Based on our reflections, we decided to continue acting on multiple directions that, all together, will allow us to improve even the effectiveness and visibility of our workshops. On the one side, we will invest on the population of project mini-sites and on the retransmission of the news produced by the projects. On the other side, we will try to involve the projects in the writing of common white papers and other publications, and we will solicit the creation of discussion groups and interest groups in our digital forum. To experiment with different workshop settings, we plan to run the next workshop in presence, trying to collocate it with some other initiative. Additionally, we plan to alternate in-presence and online events and to adopt different schedules to try to cover the needs of the whole potential audience.

5 Conclusions

The SwForum.eu workshops are providing a useful space for researchers, industry representatives, and end users to share their content, knowledge, and informed opinions on the most important software-related issues in the European Research Area. Contributors to the discussion groups can help to determine future directions for the Software Technology in Europe. While the first workshop has been useful for the support action to gather visibility and for the audience to solicit the discussion around the important themes of open source and trustworthiness, the second workshop has been focusing more on organizational reflections. In particular, we discussed the about following issues:

1. How to build a community that supports that idea?
2. How to build the actual infrastructure on top of the existing infrastructure?
3. Can we reuse from other disciplines (Medicine, Genetics, Biology, ...)?
4. What can be a sustainable funding-model?

The Software community as a whole could improve the research on specialized tools for analysis software, tools for combining, analysing and visualising (in terms of reach, replicability, transparency) by promoting the cooperation among multiple actors to create an integrated ecosystem.

The three pillars of the SwForum.eu (digital infrastructures, software engineering and cybersecurity) were addressed by the challenges presented and by the projects represented in the SwForum.eu workshops:

- With the discussion on the ecosystem for analysis software we aimed at creating a community for building an infrastructure for integration and sharing of scientific workflows on top of shared software (Engineering) data.
- With the discussion on Infrastructure as Code cost and performance optimization we aimed at identifying the concepts, criteria and tools relevant to this problem.
- With the discussion on the role of AI in the edge-to-cloud context we aimed at finding points of collaboration with other projects that work in the same field.

Collaboration among the projects can be seen from two perspectives:

- Technical collaboration. In this case SwForum.eu can act as facilitator helping projects identifying collaboration opportunities.
- Cross-fertilization through initiatives such as SwForum.eu. One of the assets offered by SwForum.eu is the Online SwForum.eu to create interesting discussions about cross projects topics and the Projects' Hub where the projects can have their own mini-sites.

6 References

- [1] E. Di Nitto et al. Software Engineering for Services and Applications: Current and Future Challenges. White Paper by the Software Engineering for Services and Applications Cluster. November 2017 <https://eucloudclusters.files.wordpress.com/2017/11/se4sa-contribution-to-wp-2020-2027.pdf>.
- [2] Georg von Krogh, Eric von Hippel, (2006) The Promise of Research on Open Source Software. Management Science 52(7):975-983. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1060.0560>.
- [3] Massimo G. Colombo, Evila Piva, Cristina Rossi-Lamastra, Open innovation and within-industry diversification in small and medium enterprises: The case of open source software firms, Research Policy, Volume 43, Issue 5, 2014, Pages 891-902, ISSN 0048-7333, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.08.015>.
- [4] del Bianco, Vieri & Lavazza, Luigi & Morasca, Sandro & Taibi, Davide. (2011). A Survey on Open Source Software Trustworthiness. IEEE Software. 28. 67 - 75. 10.1109/MS.2011.93.

Annex 1: links to the material relevant for the two workshops

- First workshop
 - Link to the presentations from the First SwForum.eu workshop:
 - <https://swforum.trust-it-services.dev/workshop-programme>
 - Link to the first workshop proceedings: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2878/>
 - Link to the videos of workshop presentations: <https://swforum.trust-it-services.dev/outreach/videos-podcasts/swforumeu-workshop-2021>
- Second workshop
 - Link to the program <https://swforum.eu/events/second-swforumeu-workshop>
 - Link to the video presentations: <https://swforum.eu/events/second-swforumeu-workshop>